

DELAMINATION: FROM INITIATION TO FINAL FAILURE

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

A unique failure/damage mode of laminated materials is delamination, a separation of the individual layers which constitute the structure. Delamination of composite structures is one of the many modes of damage in the complex failure process of these structures. This failure mode occurs in a thin layer (on the order of a fiber diameter in graphite/epoxy) of matrix material which exists between each ply [1] referred to as the interply layer and is the result of interlaminar stresses. These interlaminar stresses generally arise due to the mismatch in elastic constants from ply to ply [2]. The occurrence of delamination can significantly increase the structural compliance of a component and can lead to the ultimate failure of the part via interaction with other failure modes. This failure via delamination often occurs at loads well below those achievable if only in-plane damage and failure mechanisms are at work [3].

The stage at which delamination occurs within a laminate is dependent on the material properties, geometric characteristics, and specifics of loading of the laminate. Interlaminar strength is a key material property which determines the onset of delamination. The layup of the laminate combined with the loading conditions and the structural features which result in stress gradients within the laminate, form the geometric characteristics which control the process of delamination. Some examples of the geometric characteristics responsible for delamination are free edges, discontinuities within the laminates such as ply dropoffs, and fastener location. In addition, interlaminar stresses and thus delamination can arise in any gradient stress field in a composite laminate [4]. The layup of the laminate, in association with the geometric characteristics, is a principal determinant of the state of stress at such critical regions.

Delamination is not limited to laboratory type specimens, but manifests itself in typical composite structures as well. Experience in the NASA ACEE program with the composite vertical fin for the L-1011 aircraft indicated that the failure of the part was prompted by out-of-plane stresses [5]. The use of laminated composite media in structures thus presents the designer with the challenge of understanding this failure mode and effectively designing for it. This requires an understanding of the failure/damage mode, of how it interacts with other failure/damage modes, of the causes of delamination, and of the ramifications of its existence in a structure.

Delamination can be an intermediate or initial stage in the damage process in a laminated structure. The failure of a laminate as prompted by delamination can generally be divided into three stages as illustrated in Figure 1: one, the initiation of delamination; two, the growth of the delamination with or without interaction with other associated modes such as matrix cracking; and three, final failure of the laminate, often by in-plane mechanisms [6].

This process begins with the prediction of the initiation of delamination. Two basic approaches have been developed: one based on strain energy [7,8] and the other based on a strength of materials approach [9,10]. Subsequent to initiation, delamination growth is normally associated with the growth of matrix cracks/splits in the plies above or below the ply interface which has delaminated. This has been commonly observed in laminates with 90° plies, but a somewhat similar phenomenon occurs in

Figure 1. The stages of failure prompted by delamination.

laminates with angled plies such as $[\pm\theta]_s$, $[\pm\theta_n/0_n]_s$, and $[0_n/\pm\theta_n]_s$. Clear procedures do not exist to predict the observed interacting growth of the in-plane and out-of-plane damage modes and for the prediction of the overall load-carrying capability of the configuration. Furthermore, the relative importance of each of these modes is not known.

The work done to date is examined. This includes the well-established work on the prediction of delamination initiation as well as initial steps to extend models to the growth phase of the overall process. Experimental work to understand the basic mechanisms is also examined including efforts to assess the relative importance of the individual components of damage during growth. An assessment of the current state of the art is made and recommendations for future work put forth.

Keywords: Damage progression, delamination, matrix cracking, delamination initiation, delamination growth, final failure.

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